

THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF THE TEACHER AND HIS ROLE IN THE MANAGEMENT OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS.

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Annotation . This article pedagogue professional competence importance which out of need come coming out , his education quality in raising place where level the fact that about thought walks. From this except today's 21st century pedagogue time on demand suitable , competitive education in giving exactly which to competencies have to be PISA studies should to the results relied on without statement does .

Key words : PISA studies, professional competence , class " generator " , innovation, creativity , competitiveness education.

Abstract. This article reflects on the importance of the professional competence of the pedagogue, the importance of it and its role in improving the quality of education. In addition today's 21st century pedagogue outlines exactly what competencies should have in competitive education, in line with the demand of the times, with reference to the results of PISA studies.

Keywords : PISA studies, professional competence, class "generator", innovator, creativity, competitive education.

Education and upbringing the basis , the foundation - the school , the school school who does strength while knowledgeable and capable are teachers .

M.SH Mirziyoyev

The last in years education and training about incomparable measures done is increasing . Of these all of them in our republic education system reform make it _ new to the step take output , education quality efficiency increase in order to done is being increased . In general in education _ quality indicators only material is creating to sources does it depend or him another factors also determine does he give of Indonesia foreign from the villages in one at school take went studies analysis when done students knowledge level very low . _ Of this main reason analysis when done, of the science teacher in the class lesson in the process in activity one how much necessary of skills low the fact that determined . This is activity today modern in speech pedagogue of your profession professional recognition as competence it's happening . Professional competence what and which is it out of need come it turns out, his importance where level , it is said to questions answer Giving is important first . _

Today's competitive education system in formation pedagogue professional competence very important task just done non-stop , non-stop to search, from himself dissatisfaction of feeling appear motivation to be will be

Competence of the word one how much dictionary meanings there is . **Competence** (Latin : *competo* - I am achieving , I am worthy , I am worthy) is specific state body (local himself himself manage organ) or official of the person law , statute or another document

with defined powers , rights and duties scope ; 2) he or this in the field knowledge , experience . [1] This concept is from the late 1960s and late 1970s starting from apply started _ Known one in the field effective and efficient the work take to go for of the specialist enough to knowledge have to be and this about preparation to be placed is a requirement . That 's it preparation level enough that it is not education in the process expected of the result that it cannot be achieved reason will be So , a pedagogue professional competence one how much in characters sure manifestation will be Some in sources 3 core competencies type existence it is said .

1. *Base competence*
2. *General competence*
3. *Private competence*

An example as mother language and literature science teachers for important has been one how much competence signs available and they education process organize make and effective the result for very important. First speech competence about stopping if I pass , to the goal according to it would be . Speaking competence 4 main the component own into takes and that principles language literacy for important is considered

1. Listening comprehension (in the audio text heard the information understand)
2. Speaking skill (something topic on the surface monologue, dialogue create own personal thoughts, worldviews demonstration do it get)
3. Reading (scientific , artistic, official , popular method in the texts main the idea or the goal understanding)
4. Writing (dictation, statement , essay, formal documents write get the words spelling without error sounds and letters proportionality with spelling to literacy compliance by doing write get).

Above of skills in the pupil there is to be for in class lesson process organize doing pedagogue , first of all , this of principles application , technique with depends to skills i.e to competencies have to be need _ In my opinion , the lesson take going teacher example class "generator" part it is necessary What is this mean ? Without a generator big devices activity as stopped , to the process initiative doing in the pedagogue this skills can't be it is education quality does not rise . Innovation . This is a pedagogue for why important and his how relevance is there The quality of education in lifting pedagogue speech from the following to factors relying on need _

- ✓ Effectiveness
- ✓ Accuracy
- ✓ Purity
- ✓ From London
- ✓ Reliability
- ✓ Evidence
- ✓ Word wealth
- ✓ Persistence

Above what was said based on passable If I am , each of them speech competence surface to bring with together in class the process is the most effective management. Teacher own his opinion statement while doing, being told in information to the audience effect to hold acquisition and students to physiology monad to be need. Speech in the composition uncertain has been sentences want to give has been from the target the student distracts.

Information delivering pedagogue in his speech vulgarity, barbarism, parasite of words application pedagogue speech purity defect delivers. Such words to the core an insult words, Uzbek in the language alternative be standing up his instead of another from languages come in came the words application, memory temporary sentences analysis do it without taking while remaining his place pressing standing " break " words enters _ Given of information sure from the center turning around past walking speech to London effect does . The idea speaking person always own speech to others convince to know need, etc without listener this of your opinion after does not follow . Trust with to be told for thoughts vital examples with evidence need. If the pedagogue one said 5 minutes per sentence between again again If he repeats, his so much elegance and polish decreased keeps going Because the child's attention every time to the news aspirational and requires proof, repeated thoughts and without evidence sentences in the student interest and attention another things with exchange for reason to be can. Above requirements have has been speech, of course, persistence with done is increased.

Saying passed speech to competence to be placed from requirements apparently education process efficient manage for each _ pedagogue navigation without skills to the goal reach a little difficult will be

Teacher professional of competence again one principle this right reasoning walk get of skill existence.

Uzbekistan Republic Ministers " People " of the court education in the system education quality evaluation in the field international studies organize reach measures on " Decision No. 997 of December 8, 2018 with Uzbekistan Republic Ministers Court in the presence of Education quality control to do state inspection in the presence of Education quality evaluation according to international studies done increase The National Center 1 was established mature, education quality evaluation according to international in studies participation reach by Progress in International Reading and Literacy Study (PIRLS)

- 4th grade students the text reading and comprehension level assessment;

The Program for International Student Assessment - (PISA) is 15 years old of students reading, math and science direction from the sciences literacy level evaluation such as priority in criteria the following international evaluation programs according to international studies organize reach marked

PISA - The Program for International Student Assessment - 15 years old of students reading, math and science direction from the sciences literacy level assessment;

International PISA assessment The results will be announced on December 5, 2023 done. [3]

To him according to Uzbekistan in education in students reading literacy with 336 points on Cambodia from the state one ahead the fact that determined. This at the point reading literacy about the definition by entering transition it is necessary In the 2018 PISA studies reading to literacy as follows definition is given Reading literacy of a person own forward put goals reach in society participation reach and own knowledge and capabilities development for text in the form of from the data use, they on reasoning conduct, they with performance and understanding means _ [4] Accordingly to say may have been read from the text received information according to reasoning to do skill very low. That 's right mechanism of pedagogues in itself limping, the reason reading literacy technique apply with depends skill,

experience reasoning scarcity is doing Initially pedagogue in the text information with work qualification have to be need. For this the following to questions answer to find need.

- Reading text contained information what about ?
- Key words which one
- The author which the idea before is he driving ?
- The goal what ?
- From information being asked question why accent is giving
- *Hidden to the characters based on fact and opinion between differences installation .*

First of all , a pedagogue reasoning do it get to the skill have to be need. If the lesson in the process teacher texts analysis to do to the students above in sequence imbibe If so , in the next steps this in students skill harvest does.

Summary by doing in other words , a lesson minutes organize doing pedagogue this of the lesson manager he is in himself there is to knowledge approached without organize does _ Education quality while his speech competence , judgment competence , management and follow-up competence , what they taught while stage stage apply get competence with depend. So as a teacher of every subject above to competencies have to be for relentlessly own on spinach , to the news aspiration , creativity abilities to work to lower, to be careful his education in the process to the goal melting are the most important for

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